

Table A.1. Immune-related adverse events by system and CTCAE (version 5.0) severity

Immune-related adverse events	Mild (CTCAE grade 1–2)		Severe (CTCAE grade ≥3)	
	N = 161	%	N = 85	%
Blood and lymphatic system disorders	2	1.2	6	7.1
Cardiac disorders	0	0	3	3.5
Endocrine disorders	40	24.8	2	2.4
Gastrointestinal disorders	16	9.9	17	20
General disorders and administration site conditions	9	5.6	0	0
Hepatobiliary disorders	29	18	18	21.2
Immune system disorders	0	0	4	4.7
Metabolism and nutrition disorders	5	3.1	1	1.2
Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	10	6.2	2	2.4
Nervous system disorders	3	1.9	0	0
Renal and urinary disorders	5	3.1	3	3.5
Respiratory, thoracic, and mediastinal disorders	17	10.6	21	24.7
Skin and subcutaneous tissue disorders	25	15.5	8	9.4

Abbreviations: CTCAE, Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events

Table A.2. Univariate and multivariable Fine–Gray regression models of the association between CT-assessed sarcopenia and any immune-related adverse events, stratified by treatment line.

Strata	sdHR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (first-line) ^a	0.62	0.38	1.03	0.067
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (second line and further) ^a	0.71	0.42	1.19	0.196
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (first-line) ^b	0.51	0.27	0.96	0.037*
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (second line and further) ^b	0.70	0.41	1.22	0.223
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (first-line) ^c	0.44	0.23	0.82	0.011*
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (second and further line) ^c	0.77	0.43	1.35	0.363

a. Model 1: Univariable

b. Model 2: Adjusted for age, gender, stage, performance status, and BMI.

c. Adjusted for age, gender, stage, performance status, BMI, and combined treatment.

* Statistically significant, p value <0.05

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CT, computed tomography; sdHR, sub-distribution hazard ratio; LCI, lower confidence interval; UCI, upper confidence interval

Table A.3. Univariate and multivariable Fine–Gray regression models of the association between CT-assessed sarcopenia and severe immune-related adverse events, stratified by treatment line.

Strata	sdHR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (first-line) ^a	0.89	0.38	2.10	0.796
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (second-line and further) ^a	0.70	0.34	1.45	0.341
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (first-line) ^b	0.83	0.29	2.43	0.742
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (second-line and further) ^b	0.64	0.27	1.47	0.294
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (first-line) ^c	0.82	0.28	2.45	0.723
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (second-line and further) ^c	0.71	0.29	1.71	0.441

a. Univariate

b. Model 2: Adjusted for age, gender, stage, performance status, and BMI

c. Adjusted for age, gender, stage, performance status, BMI, and combined treatment.

* Statistically significant, p value <0.05

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CT, computed tomography; sdHR, sub-distribution hazard ratio; LCI, lower confidence interval; UCI, upper confidence interval

Table A.4. Univariate and multivariable Fine–Gray regression models of the association between CT-assessed sarcopenia and any immune-related adverse events, stratified by cancer stage.

Strata	sdHR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage III) ^a	0.70	0.20	2.47	0.580
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage IV) ^a	0.59	0.40	0.86	0.006*
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage III) ^b	0.88	0.13	6.00	0.900
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage IV) ^b	0.59	0.38	0.89	0.013*
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage III) ^c	0.82	0.13	5.17	0.837
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage IV) ^c	0.59	0.39	0.91	0.018*

a. Model 1: Univariable

b. Model 2: Adjusted for age, gender, performance status, and BMI

c. Model 3: Adjusted for age, gender, performance status, BMI, line of treatment, and combined treatment

*Statistically significant, p value <0.05

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CT, computed tomography; sdHR, sub-distribution hazard ratio; LCI, lower confidence interval; UCI, upper confidence interval

Table A.5. Univariate and multivariable Fine–Gray regression models of the association between CT-assessed sarcopenia and severe immune-related adverse events, stratified by cancer stage.

Strata	sdHR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage III) ^a	1.12	0.11	11.34	0.919
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage IV) ^a	0.70	0.40	1.24	0.229
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage III) ^b	10.71	1.29	89.10	0.028*
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage IV) ^b	0.68	0.36	1.30	0.241
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage III) ^c	2.91	0.20	42.31	0.433
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic (stage IV) ^c	0.71	0.37	1.40	0.331

a. Model 1: Univariable

b. Model 2: Adjusted for age, gender, performance status, and BMI

c. Model 3: Adjusted for age, gender, performance status, BMI, line of treatment, and combined treatment

*Statistically significant, p value <0.05

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CT, computed tomography; sdHR, sub-distribution hazard ratio; LCI, lower confidence interval; UCI, upper confidence interval

Table A.6. Univariate and multivariable Cox regression models of the association between CT-assessed sarcopenia and overall survival.

Comparison	HR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic*	1.23	0.91	1.67	0.175
Sarcopenic vs non-sarcopenic**	0.96	0.68	1.36	0.832

*Univariable

**Adjusted for age, gender, stage, performance status, and BMI

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CT, computed tomography; HR, hazard ratio; LCI, lower confidence interval; UCI, upper confidence interval

Table A.7. Association of Body Mass Index (BMI) with the development of any-grade and severe immune related adverse events (irAEs), and overall survival (OS).

Variable	Any grade irAEs				Severe irAEs				Overall survival			
	sdHR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value	sdHR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value	HR	95% LCI	95% UCI	p value
BMI (kg/m ²) ^a	1.02	0.99	1.05	0.275	1.01	0.97	1.05	0.680	0.96	0.94	0.99	0.006*
BMI (kg/m ²) ^b	1.01	0.98	1.05	0.346	1.01	0.97	1.05	0.655	0.97	0.94	0.99	0.012*
BMI (kg/m ²) ^c	1.01	0.98	1.04	0.536	1.01	0.97	1.05	0.653	0.97	0.95	1.00	0.036*

a. Model 1: Univariable

b. Model 2: Adjusted for age, gender, and performance status

c. Model 3: Adjusted for age, gender, performance status, line of treatment, and combined treatment

*Statistically significant, p value <0.05

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CT, computed tomography; sdHR, sub-distribution hazard ratio; HR, hazard ratio; LCI, lower confidence interval; UCI, upper confidence interval